

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Annex 3.2 to AD4.1 – General Survey Questionnaire for Teenagers (12 – 17 years)

WP 4

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under Grant Agreement No 101057014.

Technical reference

Work package	WP4 - Monitoring and Exposure
Task	T 4.1 - Human Biomonitoring S4.1.1.1 - Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct
Dissemination level ¹	VITO/ISCIH
Lead Beneficiary/ Responsible AE	SpF
Co-authors	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be; Eva Govarts /VITO/ eva.govarts@vito.be; Anskje VAN MENSEL /PIH/ Anskje.VANMENSEL@provincieantwerpen.be; Elly DEN HOND /PIH/ Elly.DENHOND@provincieantwerpen.be
Contributing Participants	Catherine Gabriel (AUTH); Beatriz Gonzalez-Alzaga; Marina Lacasaña (EASP); Natalie Von Goetz; Céline Fragnière Rime (FOPH); Joan O. Grimalt (IDAEA-CSIC); Sonia Namorado (INSA); Noelia Dominguez-Morueco (ISCIH); Janja Snoj Tratnik; Darja Mazej; Neža Palir (JSI); Maria Torres Toda (LNS); Loreta Strumylaitė, Justina Vaitkevičiūtė (LSMU); Andromachi Katsonouri (MOH-CY/SGL); Manca Ahačič; Lucija Perharič; Maja Martinčič, Katja Rostohar (NIJZ); Annelies DeDecker (PIH); Inese Martinsone; Svetlana Lakisa; Zanna Martinsone (RSU); Margaux Riou (SpF); Erika Zardin; Paal Graff; Steen Mollerup (STAMI); Lara Lehtoranta (THL); Aimonen Kukka; Simo Porras; Tina Santonen (TTL); Rosa Lange (UBA); Maria Wennberg (UMU); Arja Rautio (UOULU); Vladimíra Puklová; Andrea Krsková (SZU-CZ); Jurgen Buekers (VITO)
Deliverables	30 June 2023
Actual submission date	22 June 2023

¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other program participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/Institutions	Short description of changes
Version 1	2023-06-22	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	
Version 2	2023-07-11	Hardiesse Bessonneau /SpF/ Hardiesse.BESSONNEAU@santepubliquefrance.fr; Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after external review of AD4.1
Version 3	2023-09-18	Liese Gilles /VITO/ liese.gilles@vito.be	Small adaptations after GS partners' review of the questionnaires

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

Table of Contents

Technical reference _____	7
Document history _____	8
Table of Contents _____	10
I.00: Questionnaire information _____	11
I.01: Personal information _____	11
I.02: Sociodemographic information _____	12
I.03: Dietary habits _____	15
I.04: Lifestyle _____	35
I.05: Residential environment and home exposures _____	50
I.06: Occupational exposures _____	63
I.07: Health status _____	66

This survey is designed to be completed by teenagers ages 12 to 17 with assistance of an interviewer. We recommend conducting the interview with the teenagers individually. Parents/legal guardians may be able to provide background information to certain statements of the teenager that will help determine the context of these statements. The survey can also be adapted for self-administration.

I.00: Questionnaire information

- Q093: Id (participant) _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q094: Id (interviewer) _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q095: Date of the interview (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.1: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q095.3: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q098: Interview place / interview platform _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

I.01: Personal information

- Q001: What sex was the child assigned at birth?
 Male
 Female
 Intersexual
(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q002: What is the child's birth date? (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.1: Year _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.2: Month _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
 Q002.3: Day _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)
Q099: How do you identify yourself with respect to gender?
 Male
 Female
 Transgender
 Non-binary
 Other
 I don't want to put myself in a gender
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
 Q099.1: Specify other _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q119: Do you live with your parent(s) or legal guardian(s)?
 No
 Yes
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.02: Sociodemographic information

Q003: In which country was the child born? _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004: How long have you been living...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year) and your current address(es). Please indicate all addresses if you are in shared custody/parenting and the time spent in each address. (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.1: In this country (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.1.2: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.2: In your current address (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.2.1: Years _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.2.1: Months _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4: Do you live at more than one address?

Yes

No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.1: Address 1 details (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.1.1: Street name and number _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.1.2: Postal code _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2: Address 2 details (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2.1: Street name and number _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q004.4.2.2: Postal code _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005: What is the highest level of education you attained? If you live with your parents, please also indicate your parents' /legal guardians' level of education (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.1: You (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.1.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.1.2: Specify other _____ (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3: Parent 1 or legal guardian (Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.3.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.3.3: Role

Mother

Father

Legal guardian

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.4: In case parents are not living together. New partner of the parent 1. **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.4.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.4.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.5: Parent 2 or legal guardian **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.5.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)

Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)

Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)

Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)

Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)

Other

Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.5.3: Role

Mother

Father

Legal guardian

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.6: In case parents are not living together. New partner of the parent 2. **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q005.6.1: Level

No formal education or below primary education (iscd 0)

Primary education (iscd 1)

Lower secondary education, or second stage of basic education (iscd 2)

Upper secondary education (iscd 3)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Post-secondary non-tertiary education (iscd 4)
- Short-cycle tertiary education (iscd 5)
- Bachelor's or equivalent level (iscd 6)
- Master's or equivalent level (iscd 7)
- Doctoral or equivalent level (iscd 8)
- Other
- Not applicable

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q005.6.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q007: What ethnic origin does the child have? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q007.1: Origin

- Caucasian
- Arab (including north africa and the middle east)
- Sub-saharan african
- Latin-american
- South asian (including pakistan)
- Far east asia (including china and the philippines)
- Mixed/multiracial
- Other
- Do not know
- Do not wish to answer

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q007.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q008: Which language(s) is (are) spoken at home? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q008.1: National language(s) [country of study]

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q008.2: Another language

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q008.3: Specify language(s) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q100: Were the child's biological parents born in the same country as he/she? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.1: Mother

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.1.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q100.2: Father

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q100.2.1: Please specify if in another country _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q101: What is the main labour status of your parents/legal guardians (if applicable)? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q101.1: Parent 1 or legal guardian

- Employee working full-time
- Employee working part-time
- Self-employed working full-time (including family worker)

- Self-employed working part-time (including family worker)
- Unemployed
- Pupil, student, further training, unpaid work experience
- In retirement or in early retirement or has given up business
- Permanently disabled or/and unfit to work
- In compulsory military community or service
- Fulfilling domestic tasks and care responsibilities
- Other inactive person
- Other status
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q101.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.03: Dietary habits

Q009: How often did the child consume the following food categories in the last 12 months? Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q009.1: Fish and seafood

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.2: Meat

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.3: Dairy products

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.5: Cereals

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.6: Fats (eg. Oil, butter, ...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.7: Vegetables

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.8: Fruits

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.9: Snacks (e.G. Potato chips, bars, crackers...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q009.10: Nuts

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 meals / month
- 1-3 meals / week
- 4-6 meals / week
- 1 or more meals / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011: Did the child eat fish or other seafood items in the last 14 days?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011.1: How often did you consume the following seafood and fish species items in the last 14 days?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011.1.1: White fish (e.G. Hake, snapper, sea bream, cod, haddock, grouper, halibut, tilapia, bass, ...)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011.1.2: Small oily fish (e.G. Anchovy, sardines, salmon)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q011.1.3: Big oily fish (e.G. Sword fish, tuna, school shark)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q011.1.4: Other sea food (e.G. Octopus, squid, shrimp, scampi)

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012: How often did the child consume the following food items in the last 12 months? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1: Eggs **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.1.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2: Cabbages **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.2.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3: Cucurbitaceae (cucumber, pumpkins, zucchini) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.3.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4: Beans, peas and lentils **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.4.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.4.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5: Orchard fruits (apples, pears, plums, figs...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.5.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6: Strawberries **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.6.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7: Other berries (grapes, blueberries...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.7.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8: Dried fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.8.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.8.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.9: Ready meals (in plastic packaging) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.9.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.10: Fast food **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.10.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11: Rice **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.11.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.11.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12: Other cereals (barley, oats, bran, wheat, rye, maize) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.12.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.12.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13: Mushrooms **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.13.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.13.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14: Potatoes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.14.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.14.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15: Leafy vegetables (e.G. Spinach, romaine lettuce, kale, swiss chard, endives, collard greens...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.15.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16: Wild game meat **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.16.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.16.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17: Offal **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.17.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.17.2: Portion sizes

- A
- B
- C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.18: Processed meat (ham, sausage, bacon, deli meats (such as bologna, smoked turkey and salami), hot dogs, jerky, pepperoni) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.18.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.18.2: Portion sizes

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.19: Meat substitutes (eg: tofu) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q012.19.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q012.19.2: Portion sizes

A

B

C

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q013: In the past 12 months, how often were the eggs that the child ate from your own hens or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers?

0% (never)

Less than 25% of the time

25% - 50% of the time

50% - 75% of the time

More than 75% of the time

100% (always)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q015: How does the child usually eat vegetables and fruits? **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q015.1: Vegetables

Without skin

With skin

Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q015.2: Fruits

Without skin

With skin

Both with skin and without skin

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017: Did the child consume organic food in the last 12 months?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q017.1: How often did the child usually consume organic food in the last 12 months?

<1 / month

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q017.2: Which percentage of the child's diet is based on organic food? Indicate a percentage for each of the following food items (0%= nothing organic and 100%= all the food consumed is organic) Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q017.2.1: Vegetables

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.2: Fruits

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.3: Bread

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.4: Meat

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.5: Eggs

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.6: Dairy products

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.7: Rice, pasta and other cereals

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8: Other foods

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q017.2.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q018: Did the child eat vegetables and/or fruit from your own garden or received/bought from neighbours, friends, family or local growers in the last 12 months? If yes, indicate per season the portion you have eaten locally-grown products (0%= nothing and 100%= all fruit/vegetables is from local sources) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1: Fruits **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.1.1: Winter

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.1.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2: Vegetables **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q018.2.1: Winter

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.2: Spring

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.3: Summer

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q018.2.4: Autumn

- 0% (never)
- Less than 25% of the time
- 25% - 50% of the time
- 50% - 75% of the time
- More than 75% of the time
- 100% (always)
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q019A: How much water do you drink on average each day? (do also think of water in hot beverages and soups!)

- Less than 1 l/day
- 1-2 l/day
- 2-3 l/day
- 3-5 l/day
- More than 5 l/day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020: What is the main source of the child's water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.1: Water for drinking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.2: Water for cooking

- Public network
- Bottled water (plastic)
- Bottled water (glass)
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q020.3: Water for showering

- Public network
- Private well
- Others
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q020.3.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021: Do you use water purification devices or water filtering systems for the child's water? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.1: Water for drinking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener
- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.1.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q021.2: Water for cooking

- Filter (faucet attachment, refrigerator filter)
- Water softener
- Other
- No treatment
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q021.2.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q022: In which of the following bottling types does the child usually drink beverages? Please consider all beverages (fruit juices, ice tea, soft drinks...) including water (multiple answers possible) Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.1: Beverages in glass bottling

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.2: Beverages in plastic bottling

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.3: Beverages from decorated colored glass

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.4: Canned beverages

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.5: Drinks prepared in metal recipients (e.G. Arabic teapot)

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q022.6: Other types

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q022.6.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q022.7: Don't know

Yes

No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q023: Do you use the following containers for keeping the child's food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q023.1: Hard plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.2: Soft plastic container

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.3: Baking paper

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.4: Plastic bag

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.5: Aluminium containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.6: Ceramic containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.7: Glass containers

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week
- 4 – 6/ week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8: Others

- (nearly) never
- 1 / month
- 2 – 3/ month
- 1 – 3/ week

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q023.8.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024: Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating the child's food in the microwave oven? If yes, how often do you use it? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q024.1: Hard plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.2: Soft plastic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.3: Ceramic containers

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4: Others

(nearly) never

1 / month

2 – 3/ month

1 – 3/ week

4 – 6/ week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q024.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q025: What materials do you use as cookware for cooking and frying (e.G. Pots, pans, fryer, robots, making bread machine etc.) Choose from the following options: **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q025.1: Steel

(nearly) never

1 / month

2-3 / month

1 / week

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 2-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q025.2: Ceramic
- (nearly) never
 - 1 / month
 - 2-3 / month
 - 1 / week
 - 2-3 / week
 - 4-6 / week
 - Daily
 - Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q025.3: Glass
- (nearly) never
 - 1 / month
 - 2-3 / month
 - 1 / week
 - 2-3 / week
 - 4-6 / week
 - Daily
 - Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q025.4: Teflon baking tray/covered pan
- (nearly) never
 - 1 / month
 - 2-3 / month
 - 1 / week
 - 2-3 / week
 - 4-6 / week
 - Daily
 - Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q025.5: Others
- Yes
 - No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q025.5.1: Frequency
- (nearly) never
 - 1 / month
 - 2-3 / month
 - 1 / week
 - 2-3 / week
 - 4-6 / week
 - Daily
 - Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q025.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q025.6: Don't know [] **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q026: Does the child consume dietary supplements (e.G. Vitamins and minerals)?

Checked

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1: If yes, please indicate type, frequency and duration. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.1: Vitamin a

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q026.1.1.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.1.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.1.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.2: Vitamin b/ b-complex

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.2.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.2.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.2.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.3: Vitamin c

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.3.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.3.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.3.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.4: Vitamin d

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q026.1.4.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.4.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.4.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.5: Vitamin e

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.5.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.5.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.5.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.6: Iron

No

Yes

Don't know

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.6.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.6.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.6.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.7: Zinc

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.7.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.7.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.7.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.8: Selenium

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.8.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.8.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.8.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.9: Calcium

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q026.1.9.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.9.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.9.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q026.1.10: Fish oil

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.10.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.10.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.10.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.11: Folic acid

No

Yes

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.11.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.11.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.11.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.12: Algae or seaweed supplement

No

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.12.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.12.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.12.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.13: Multivitamins supplement

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.13.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.13.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.13.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.14: Multiminerals supplement

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.14.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.14.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.14.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.15: Omega-3 fatty acid supplements

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.15.1: Dose of vitamin/supplement per serving/dosing _____

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.15.2: Frequency (dosing/week) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.15.3: Duration(months/years) _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q026.1.16: Other supplements

- No
 Yes
 Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q026.1.16.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q027: How often did the child eat dishes from communal catering, such as from a canteen, dining hall or cafeteria in the last 4 weeks?

- (nearly) never
 2 – 3/ month
 1 – 3/ week
 4 – 6/ week
 1 / day
 2 or more / day

7 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q107: In the last 4 weeks, did you consume fast food and ready meals (prepared dishes as frozen pizza and the like)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

(please consider also beverages)?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1: If yes, how was it packed and how often did he/she consume it? Per type of pack:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.1: In cardboard box

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.2: In paper

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.3: In paper cup

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.4: In plastic cup

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.5: In plastic (e.G. Bag, box)

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.6: In polystyrene foam (e.G. Box)

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q107.1.7: In aluminium containers

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- Daily
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.04: Lifestyle

Q028: In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describe your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen. Choose from the following options: **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1: Have you ever smoked?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q028.1.1: I was a smoker but i gave up smoking

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.1: Age start smoking **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.1.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.1.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2: Age stop smoking **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.2.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3: Type/variety and average of consumption **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.1.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.2: Pipes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.2.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.2.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.3: Cigars **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.3.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.3.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.4: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.4.1: Times used per day

- Once
- 2-5 times
- 6-10 times
- More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.1.3.4.2: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.5: Hookah [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.5.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.5.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.6: Products for smoking cessation [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.6.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.6.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.7: Others [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.7.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.7.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.1.3.7.3: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2: I currently smoke

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)

Q028.1.2.1: Age start smoking **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.1.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2: Type/variety and average of consumption **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.1: Cigarettes [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.1.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.2: Pipes [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.2.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.3: Cigars [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.3.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.3.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.4: Electronic cigarettes [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.4.1: Times used per day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.2.2.4.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.5: Hookah [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.5.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.5.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.6: Products for smoking cessation [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.6.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.6.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7: Others [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.2.2.7.3: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3: I use smokeless tobacco products (e.G., snuff, dipp, chewing tobacco)

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q028.1.3.1: Age start **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.1.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q028.1.3.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2: Type/variety and average of consumption **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1: Snuff [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2: Dip [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3: Chewing tobacco [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3.1: No. Per day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q028.1.3.2.3.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029: In relation to smoking habits, how many people living in the child's house smoke or vape regularly (indoors)?
Please provide a number.

_____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1: For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked and the average times of e-cigarettes used per day indoors **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1: Member no.1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.1.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.1.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2: Member no.2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.2.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.2.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3: Member no.3 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.3.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.3.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4: Member no.4 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1: Cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1.1: No. /day _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.1.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.2: Electronic cigarettes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q029.1.4.2.1: Times /day

[] Once

[] 2-5 times

[] 6-10 times

[] More than 10 times

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q029.1.4.2.2: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q030: In general, how long, on a daily average, did the child usually spend in the following indoor places where people smoke? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q030.1: At home

[] Never

[] <1h/day

[] 1-4h/day

[] >4h/day

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q030.2: Elsewhere

[] Never

[] <1h/day

[] 1-4h/day

[] >4h/day

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q031: Do those who visit the child's house smoke indoors?

[] Never

[] Rarely (less than 1 / month)

[] Sometimes (less than 1 / week)

[] 1 / week

[] 2-3 / week

[] 4-6 / week

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q161: How often do you consume alcoholic beverages?

[] (nearly) never

[] 1 - 3 / month

[] 1 - 3 / week

[] 4 - 6 / week

[] 1 / day

[] 2 or more / day

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032: How often does the child use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand mostly used. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1: Hair products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1: Spray, lacquer, gel/mousse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.1.1: Frequency

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.2: Shampoo **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.3: Conditioner **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.4: Moisturizer cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.1.5: Dye, colour rinse **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.1.5.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.5.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.1.6: Bleaching products (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.6.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.1.7: Perming products (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.7.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.1.8: Relaxer (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.8.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.1.9: Other products (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.9.2: Specify other _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.1.9.3: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2: Cosmetics (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1: Foundation (powder, liquid) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.2: Make-up remover **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.3: Lipbalm **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.4: Lipstick **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.5: Blusher **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.2.5.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q032.2.5.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.6: Eye make-up (e.G.Mascare, eye shadow, eyeliner, mask, crayon) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.6.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.7: Nail polish (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.7.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.8: Nail polish remover (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.8.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.9: Traditional cosmetics (kohl, surma, kajal, tiro, etc.) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.2.9.2: Brand _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.10: Other products (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.10.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.2.10.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.2.10.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3: Bodycare **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1: Perfume / eau de cologne **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.1.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.1.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.2: Body soap / shower gel **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.2.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.2.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.3: Hand lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.3.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.3.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.4: Face cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.4.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.4.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.5: Face mask **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.5.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.5.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.6: Sun cream (sunscreen) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.6.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.6.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.7: Sun tan lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.7.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.7.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.8: Anti-aging cream **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.8.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.8.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.9: Anti aging cream with sun protection factor **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.9.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.9.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.10: Deodorant **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.10.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.10.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.11: Shaving cream or aftershave lotion **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.11.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.11.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.12: Body oil or body lotion (cream, milk, ...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.12.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.12.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.13: Skin bleaching products **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.13.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1-3 / month

1-3 / week

4-6 / week

1 / day

2 or more / day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.13.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.14: Mouthwash **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.14.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.14.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.15: Dental floss **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q032.3.15.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q032.3.15.2: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16: Other products **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.1: Frequency

- (nearly) never
- 1-3 / month
- 1-3 / week
- 4-6 / week
- 1 / day
- 2 or more / day
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q032.3.16.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q032.3.16.3: Brand _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q033: In the last 3 months, did you use any of the following products at home or school in diy (do-it-yourself) activities or hobbies, or were you directly or indirectly exposed to any of these substances at home or school?

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.1: Paint, varnish, lacquer, dyes, inks, pigments

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.2: Solvents, degreasers, paint removers

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.3: Seals or fillers

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.4: Glues, adhesives

- Yes

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.5: Wax (e.G., furniture, ski, horse saddles), epoxy resins

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.6: Leather cleaning products, leather preservatives

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.7: Lubricating oils (e.G., for tools, machines, bikes, music instruments, incl. Ptfе-products)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.8: Cleaning chemicals

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.9: Computer and/or electronic device repair, welding/soldering

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.10: Teflon products (e.G. Kitchen appliances)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.11: Water repellent clothing

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.12: Fireplace/combustion products (in/outdoors)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.15: Degrease tools, machines or electronics

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.16: Other products/activities

Yes

No

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q033.16.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q038: Please, indicate how much time per day, on average, the child has used electronic devices such as mobile phones, computers, tablets, gps... In the last month? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.1.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1: Portable devices (mobiles, tablets, laptops, gps...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.1.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2: Desk devices (computer desk...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q038.2.2.3: Don't know **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039: How long does you dedicate to sport and/or physical activities? Please consider all the activities (at school, after-school activities, hobbies etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q039.1: Weekdays

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q039.2: Weekends

No time

Less than 1 hour/day

1 hour/day (approx.)

2 hours/day (approx.)

3 hours/day (approx.)

4 hours/day (approx.)

> 4 hours/day

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040: Which of the following best describes the child's current physical exercise? Choose from the following options:

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1: Light physical exercise for relaxation **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.1.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.1.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2: Medium and intensive physical exercise **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.2.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.2.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3: Intensive (vigorous) physical exercise (sweating/out of breath) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q040.3.1: Frequency

(nearly) never

1 / week

A few times per week

Daily

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q040.3.2: Duration

10-30 minutes

>= 30 minutes

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q041: How often (times per day) does the child wash his/her hands?

Twice a day or less

3-6 times a day

More than 6 times a day

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q042: Does the child have a habit of putting objects made of plastic (e.G. Pens, glasses or toys) in your mouth and chewing on them?

No

Yes

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q042.1: If yes, please specify the frequency

Daily

Several times per week

Less often

Don't know

(Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q043: Does the child regularly wear plastic or rubber shoes such as e.G. Flip-flops, beach shoes, swimming shoes, crocs® or clogs without socks?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

I.05: Residential environment and home exposures

Q044: In which area is your home located?

City centre

Near city centre

Suburb/metropolitan area

Industrial

Rural/village

Other areas

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q044.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q046: Is the child's current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these facilities?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.1: Agricultural fields (including vineyards and orchards)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.2: Greenhouses

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.3: Natural spaces (parks, national parks...)

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.4: Firefighting facility, military base, airfield

No

Yes, < 150 m

Yes, 150 - 500 m

Yes, 500 - 1000 m

Yes, > 1000 m

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q046.5: Landfills, dump sites, sewage sludge treatment

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q046.6: Waste incinerator, power plant based coal, oil, gas or wood

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q046.7: Other sites where pesticides are used (e.G., golf yards, railway...)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047: Is the child's current home address and/or previous home address located near any of these industries?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.1: Chemical industry (plastics, pesticides, tannery, pigments, cement, fertilizers,...)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.2: Paper or textile industry

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q047.3: Metal industry (metals, no-ferro, steel, metal smeltery)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q047.4: Electronics (computer, electronics, photovoltaic devices, solar cells)

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q047.5: A recycling plant, scrap yard, car repair plant

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q047.6: A glass factory

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q047.7: A site where medical equipment is produced

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q047.8: Other industrial facilities

- No
- Yes, < 150 m
- Yes, 150 - 500 m
- Yes, 500 - 1000 m
- Yes, > 1000 m
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q047.8.1: Specify facility _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q048: Does your house have garden and/or vegetable garden?

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q048.1A: Has your garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q048.1B: Has your vegetable garden been treated with pesticides in the last 12 months?

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050: Has your house (inside) or your school been treated with herbicides, fungicides and/or insecticides in the last 4 weeks? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q050.1: House

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050.2: School

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q050.3: Workplace

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q052: In the last 12 months, were insecticide/pesticide products used to control or repel pest problems in your garden? (e.G. Snails/slugs, weeds, mosses/lichens, other garden pests/insects).

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053: What is the main water source for your home garden irrigation?

- Groundwater water (springs, wells)
- Private well
- Surface water (lake, river, streams, reservoir, ponds)
- Rainwater
- Others

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q053.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q054: Which of the following options best describes your home...?

- Detached house
- Semi-detached house
- Townhouse
- Flat/apartment
- A farmhouse
- Other (e.G. Caravan, mobile home)

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q054.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q055: What materials are used for most of the floor coverings in your home? **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1: Non-textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.1: Wood-parquet **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.2: Wooden planks **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.3: Laminate **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.4: Pvc **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.5: Linoleum **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q055.1.6: Tiles (e.G. Stone, marble, terrazzo) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7: Other non-textile material [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.1.7.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2: Textile flooring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.1: Synthetic fibre [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.2: Natural fibre [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.3: Natural or synthetic fibre with plastic backing [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4: Other textile material [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.2.4.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q055.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q056: Do you help with general cleaning of your home? (general cleaning includes vacuum cleaning, mopping - use of cleaners/chemicals, disinfectant products in water, sweeping, dusting)

[] No

[] Yes, entirely

[] Yes, partially

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q056.1: In that case specify the percentage he/she is in charge of _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q057: If the child uses a vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? Please, specify type and frequency of use

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.1: Type

[] Vacuum cleaner with air filter

[] Vacuum cleaner with water filter

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q057.2: Frequency

[] Less than 1 / week

[] 1 / week

[] 2 / week or more

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160: Does the child clean the home with water? Please, specify the frequency.

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q160.1: Frequency

[] Less than 1 / week

[] 1 / week

[] 2 / week or more

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058: In the last month, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week? If yes, please specify if the cleaning product generally used is a classical or eco-friendly product (product featuring an eco-label on the package) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.1: Cleaning products (e.G. For kitchen, bathroom, floor, windows)

[] No

[] Don't know

[] Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.1.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2: Floor wax

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.2.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3: Fabric softener

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.3.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4: Wood varnish

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.4.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5: Dry cleaning products (e.G. For cleaning upholstery, clothes, carpets)

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.5.1: Type of product

- Classical
- Eco-friendly
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6: Air freshener

- No
- Don't know
- Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.6.1: Type of product

- Classical

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.7: Solvents (eg: cleaning solvents are acetone, toluene and trichloroethylene-tce. Common mild solvents include isopropyl alcohol, glycerin, and propylene glycol)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.7.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8: Spot remover products

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.8.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9: Impregnation fluids (e.G. For upholstery, shoes)

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.9.1: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10: Other cleaning products

No

Don't know

Yes, once a week or more

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q058.10.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q058.10.2: Type of product

Classical

Eco-friendly

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059: How much time on average does the child spend in the following places (referred to school days and weekends)?

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.1: Fall **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.1.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Q059.1.1.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.1.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.1.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.1.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q059.1.1.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.1.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.1.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2: Weekends (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)
(Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Q059.1.2.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q059.1.2.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.1.2.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.1.2.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.1.2.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2: Winter (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1: Weekdays (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.2.1.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.2.1.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.2.1.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)
Q059.2.1.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.1.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.1.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.2.1.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.2: Weekends (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.2.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
- Q059.2.2.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)
Q059.2.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)
Q059.2.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q059.2.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q059.2.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.2.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.2.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.2.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3: Spring **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.3.1.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q059.3.1.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q059.3.1.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.1.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.1.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2: Weekends **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.2.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.2.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.2.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.3.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.3.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.3.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.4: In the family's car **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.4.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.4.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.4.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.5.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.5.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.5.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q059.3.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.3.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.3.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4: Summer **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1: Weekdays **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1: Inside your home **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.1.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.1.2: Inside other houses **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q059.4.1.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.1.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.1.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.1.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus stops...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.6.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.6.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q059.4.1.6.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.7.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.1.7.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.1.7.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2: Weekends (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.1: Inside your home (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.1.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.1.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.1.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2: Inside other houses (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.2.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.2.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3: In other indoor spaces (e.G. School, school clubs, shopping centre, sports club, cinema,restaurant...) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.3.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.3.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4: In the family's car (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.4.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.4.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5: In other closed vehicles for daily commuting (e.G. Bus, car, train...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5.1: Hours _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.5.2: Minutes _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q059.4.2.5.3: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.6: Outdoor traffic (on foot, bicycle, motorbike, skating, at train stations or bus

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

stops...) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.6.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.6.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.OPTIONAL)**

Q059.4.2.6.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.7: Outdoors, away from home (park, garden, forest, beach, outdoor sports area...)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q059.4.2.7.1: Hours _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q059.4.2.7.2: Minutes _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q059.4.2.7.3: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q061: Please complete the following information about redecorations and renovations made in your home.

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.1: Is your home currently being renovated? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows...)

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.2: Has your home been renovated in the last year? (major renovations: e.G. New walls, floor, windows...)

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q061.3: Has your home been redecorated in the last year? (e.G. Painting, varnishing...)

[] Yes

[] No

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062: How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please specify frequency of use (months/year in which mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q062.1: Mechanical ventilation system

[] No

[] Yes, always on

[] Yes, sometimes switched off

[] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2: Ventilation through opening windows or doors

[] Yes

[] No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.1: Frequency (autum-winter)

[] Nearly never

[] Less then daily

[] Daily – for a short time

[] Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)

[]

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.2.2: Frequency (spring-summer)

[] Nearly never

[] Less then daily

[] Daily – for a short time

[] Daily – for longer time (e.G. Half a day or whole day)

[]

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q062.3: Does your house have ventilation grilles in windows/doors or walls?

- No
- Yes, but they are sometimes closed
- Yes, they are always open
- Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063: Do you have any pets at home or did you have any pets at home in the last 12 months? If so, specify type and number **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q063.1: No animal **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.2: Dog

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.3: Cat

- Yes
- No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q063.3.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.4: Bird

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.4.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5: Other animal

- Yes
- No

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q063.5.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.1.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2: Specify other _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q063.5.2.1: Number _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.06: Occupational exposures

Q064: What is your occupation/profession? _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q066: Please, describe your current job _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067: How long have you been doing this job? Specify years or months, if less than one year **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067.1: Years _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q067.2: Months _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068: Do you come into contact with the following substances on your current job? Note: contact can occur via the skin and/or by inhalation. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.1: Combustion products, including gasoline/diesel exhausts, ash or soot

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.1.1: Specify: (e.G. Aluminium production, chimney sweeping, coking plants, firefighting/ fire

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

practice/ fire prevention training, foundry industry, garage work, heating/ thermal power plants, metallurgic industry, mining, vehicle inspection, vehicle depots, waste incineration) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.2: Metals (eg. Mercury, lead, cadmium, chromium, others)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.2.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.3: Paints/ coatings including varnishes

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.3.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.4: Printing inks

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.4.1: Specify: (e.G. Ink production, printing industry, other job, which?) _____

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.5: Solvents

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.5.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.6: Plasticisers and plastics

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.6.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.7: Pesticides, biocides or disinfection products (herbicides, fungicides, insecticides or bactericides)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.7.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.8: Cosmetics or hair treatment products (hair dyes etc.)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.8.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q068.9: Polymers production (monomers)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q068.9.1: Specify: plastic products production _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q068.10: Flame retardants

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.10.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.11: Photoresist/antireflective coatings

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.11.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.12: Cytotoxic drugs (e.G. Cyclophosphamide, doxorubicine, methotrexate...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.12.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.13: Anaesthetic gases (e.G. desflurane, isoflurane, nitrous oxide...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.13.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.14: Disinfection and cleaning products (e.G. Ethanol, isopropylalcohol...)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.14.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.15: E-waste (electric or electronic devices)

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.15.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.16: Plastic waste

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.16.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.17: Other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.17.1: Specify: (e.G. Contaminated soil renovation) _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q068.18: Other compounds

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q068.18.1: Specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q069: In the working environment in which you perform working tasks/activities are there technical risk management measures (e.G. Collective protective measures such as local exhaust ventilation, enclosing of the exposure source...) available?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q069.1: Please specify _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

I.07: Health status

Q073: How tall is the child (in cm)? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q074: How much does the child weight (in kg)? _____ **(Priority.BASICCODEBOOK)**

Q078: Does the child use glasses and/or contact eye lenses?

Yes, glasses

Yes, contact lenses

Yes, both

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079: Have you or any of your biological family members (father, mother, siblings, grand-mother, grand-father...) been diagnosed by a medical doctor with any of the following diseases or conditions?

if yes, has it occurred within the last 12 months? Please specify how old were you when this was first diagnosed.

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1: Asthma (allergic asthma included) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.1.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.1.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.1.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.2: Chronic bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (copd), emphysema

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.2.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.2.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.3: Myocardial infarction **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.3.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.3.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.3.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.4: Coronary heart disease (angina pectoris) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.4.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.4.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.4.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.5: High blood pressure (hypertension) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.5.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.5.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.5.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.6: Elevated blood cholesterol **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.6.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.6.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.6.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.7: Stroke (cerebral haemorrhage, cerebral thrombosis) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.7.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.7.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.7.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.8: Rheumatoid arthritis (inflammation of the joints) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.8.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.8.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.8.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.9: Osteoarthritis (arthrosis, joint degeneration) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q079.1.9.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.9.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.9.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.10: Osteoporosis **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.10.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.10.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.10.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.11: Low back disorder or other chronic back defect **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.11.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.11.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.11.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.12: Neck disorder or other chronic neck defect **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.12.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.12.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.12.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.13: Type 1 diabetes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.13.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.13.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.13.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.14: Type 2 diabetes **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.14.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q079.1.14.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.14.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.15: Thyroid disease (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.15.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.15.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.15.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.16: Allergy (any other type than the following: allergic rhinitis, allergic conjunctivitis, allergic dermatitis) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.16.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.16.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.16.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17: Allergic rhinitis (nasal itching, sneezing, runny nose, or nasal blockage)

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.17.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.17.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18: Allergic conjunctivitis (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.18.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.18.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19: Allergic dermatitis (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.19.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.19.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.20: Anaphylaxis (symptoms: airway constriction that makes it difficult to breath, shock with severe drop of blood pressure, rapid pulse, dizziness, or lightheadedness) (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q079.1.20.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.20.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.20.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.21: Stomach ulcer (gastric or duodenal ulcer) **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q079.1.21.1: You

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.21.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q079.1.21.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)**

Q079.1.22: cirrhosis or fibrosis of the liver/liver disease or dysfunction **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.22.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.22.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.22.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.23: kidney disease or dysfunction **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.23.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.23.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.23.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24: cancer (malignant tumour, also including leukaemia and lymphoma) (see next question to specify kind of cancer) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.24.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.24.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25: Severe headache such as migraine **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25.1: The child

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.25.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.25.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.26: urinary incontinence, problems in controlling the bladder or other gallbladder problems

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.26.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.26.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.26.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27: chronic anxiety **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.27.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.27.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28: Chronic depression **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.28.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.28.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.29: Other mental health problems **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.29.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.29.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.29.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.30: spinal cord disorders **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.30.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.30.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.30.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.31: attention deficit disorders (add, adhd) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q079.1.31.1: The child

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.31.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.31.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.32: Autism or autism spectrum dysfunction **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.32.1: The child
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.32.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.32.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.33: asperger syndrome **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.33.1: The child
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.33.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.33.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.34: Down syndrome or other chromosomal disorder **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.34.1: The child
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.34.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.34.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.35: neurodegenerative diseases (parkinson's disease, alzheimer's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis and etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.35.1: You
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

- Q079.1.35.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.35.2: Family member _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.36: Learning disability (dyslexia and etc.) **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
- Q079.1.36.1: The child
- Never
- Yes, in the past 12 months
- Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q079.1.36.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.36.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.37: Neurological disorders (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.37.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.37.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.37.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.38: Permanent injury or defect caused by an accident (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.38.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.38.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.38.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.39: (for girls only) gynaecological diseases (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.39.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.39.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.39.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.40: (for boys only) prostate diseases (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.40.1: You

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.40.1.1: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.40.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.41: Other diseases or conditions. (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.41.1: The child

Never

Yes, in the past 12 months

Yes, more than 12 months ago

3 = don't know

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.41.1.1: Specify other _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.41.1.2: Age at diagnosis _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q079.1.41.2: Family member _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.1.41.2.1: Specify other _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q079.2: If you answered "yes" for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer. Choose from the following options: (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

- Q079.2.1: Bladder [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.2: Blood [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.3: Bone [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.4: Breast [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.5: Cervix(cervical) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.6: Colon [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.7: Esophagus (esophageal) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.8: Brain [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.9: Gallbladder [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.10: Kidney [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.11: Larynx/windpipe [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.12: Leukaemia [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.13: Liver [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.14: Lung [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.15: Lymphoma/hodgkin's disease [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.16: Melanoma [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.17: Mouth/tongue/lip [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.18: Nervous system [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.19: Ovary(ovarian) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.20: Pancreas(pancreatic) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.21: Prostate [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.22: Rectum (rectal) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.23: Skin(non-melanoma) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.24: Skin (don't know what kind) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.25: Soft tissue (muscle or fat) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.26: Stomach [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.27: Testis (testicular) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.28: Thyroid [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.29: Uterus (uterine) [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.30: Other [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.30.1: Specify other _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q079.2.31: Don't know [] **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

Q080: During the past two weeks, has the child used any medicines or homeopathic medicines?

- [] Yes
 [] No
 [] Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1: If yes, please indicate the commercial name(s) of the medicine, for which condition, the indication, as well as the strength of the drug, dose and frequency of use. **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

- Q080.2.1.1: Medicine 1 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.4: Dose _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.5: Frequency of use _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2: Medicine 2 **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.1: Commercial name _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.2: Condition _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**
 Q080.2.1.2.3: Indication _____ **(Priority.OBLIGATORY)**

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q080.2.1.2.4: Dose _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.2.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3: Medicine 3 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.1: Commercial name _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.2: Condition _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.3: Indication _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.4: Dose _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.3.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4: Medicine 4 (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.1: Commercial name _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.2: Condition _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.3: Indication _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.4: Dose _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.4.5: Frequency of use _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.6: Starting date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q080.2.1.1.7: Ending date (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081: Have you started menstruating?

Yes

No

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q081.1: What age did the child get her first period? Age at menarche _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q108: What is your head circumference? _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q109: What was your mother's age at your birth? _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q110: Did your mother smoke while pregnant of you?

Yes

No

Do not wish to answer

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q111: Had you been breastfed when you were a baby?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q111.1: If yes, for how long have you been breastfed? Specify years or months, if less than one year

(Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q111.1.1: Years _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q111.1.2: Months _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q112: Do you have or ever had dental sealant in your teeth?

Yes

No

Don't know

(Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.1.1: In how many teeth? _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.1.2: Don't know (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2: When was the dental sealant placed last time? (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q112.2.1: Days _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

ANNEX 3.2 – GENERAL SURVEY QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TEENAGERS

Q112.2.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.2.4: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3: When was the dental sealant removed from your teeth last time? (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.1: Days _____ (Priority.OPTIONAL)

Q112.3.2: Months _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.3: Years _____ (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q112.3.4: Don't know [] (Priority.OBLIGATORY)

Q117: What was your gestational age at birth (in weeks)? The gestational age describes the time elapses between the first day of your mother's last menstrual cycle to the birth date. A normal pregnancy can range from 38 to 42 weeks.

Infants born before 37 weeks are considered premature. (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.1: Gestational age _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.2: Don't know [] (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q117.3: Refuse [] (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118: What was your weight at birth (in g) (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118.1: Weight _____ (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118.2: Don't know [] (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)

Q118.3: Refuse [] (Priority.NICE_TO_HAVE)